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ROLE OF STAKEHOLDER INTEGRATION IN PROJECT SUCCESS: A CASE OF PUBLIC SECTOR UNIVERSITIES IN KHYBER PUKHTUNKHWA, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Taking a comprehensive account of the actual stakeholders for successful infrastructural projects in the context of public sector universities has been of peculiar interest in stabilizing the higher education sector of a developing economy like Pakistan. The main purpose of this study is to explore the importance of stakeholder integration on the successful implementation of project success. Data was collected from project staff from different public sector organizations in Pakistan. Regression and correlation analysis were used to empirically test the relationship with the help of SPSS. The findings of the study revealed the fact that there is a direct relationship between stakeholder engagement and project success. The study has provided important suggestions at managerial and policy levels. Future research implications includes replication of the study on other public sector projects and inclusion of project governance as a significant intervening variable.

Key words: Stakeholder integration, project governance, project success, Pakistan.

Introduction:

Project success is highly relevant in academic and professional project management in developing countries such as Pakistan, where a well-executed project may significantly boost the economy. In such environments, a complete awareness of the factors influencing the success of a project is necessary as the diversity and complexity of the projects carried out their needs such knowledge (Eriksson et al., 2023). From this, it is abundantly evident that efficient project management depends critically on project governance and stakeholder integration. Stakeholder integration is the state of having project sponsors, team members, end users, and outside partners actively participating in the design and implementation of the project. Amiri et al. (2022) say effective stakeholder integration guarantees that all stakeholders' perspectives and needs are considered, reducing the risk of conflicts and raising the likelihood of the project's success. Research shows that including stakeholders in a project enhances communication, trust, and collaboration, directly influencing project outcomes (Plaza-Úbeda et al., 2010). Poor countries' challenges in attempting to include their citizens include cultural variations, political intervention, and lack of resources. These elements impede their ability to cooperate and make wise judgments. This study will investigate methods to remove or minimize these challenges and promote stakeholder participation to enhance project performance.

This research is motivated by the major economic crises Pakistan is going through. Particularly those sponsored by the Annual Development Program (ADP), present financial restrictions demand effective management and successful completion of development projects (Unterhitzenberger and Moeller, 2021). Projects sponsored by the ADP might improve the national economy; furthermore, the program is vital for the nation's public sector planning and development initiatives. Many projects in Pakistan fail to meet their objectives due to inadequate stakeholder participation, poor governance, and neglect of environmental sustainability and leadership dynamics (Naderpajouh et al., 2024). This study aims to solve these challenges to improve Pakistan's project management techniques. This should help to improve the social and economic development of the country. The significance of this research is in the way it could clarify all the factors influencing project performance in developing countries (Vaez-Alaei et al., 2024). While most of the literature has focused on certain aspects of project management, a limited number of studies have examined how stakeholder participation and governance interact. Examining the link between stakeholder integration, project governance, and projects' general success helps fill that information gap. The results of this study might be used by development project planners and managers in Pakistan and other similar environments to guide their activities.

The objectives of this research is: to evaluate the impact of stakeholder integration on

project success.

This study is organized in the following way. In section 2, detailed literature is discussed regarding the under study variables. Section 3 discusses the methodology. Whereas section 4 discusses the data analysis while section 5 discusses the findings recommendation and conclusion.

Literature Review.

Impact of Stakeholder Integration on Project Success

In many different fields, effective projects now depend on the involvement of stakeholders in ever-increasing significance. The idea is about including stakeholders in project decisions and adhering to their expectations, concerns, and interests throughout the project lifetime (Wu et al., 2023). Stakeholders here might be both internal—that of employees, managers, and project team members—and external—that of consumers, suppliers, government agencies, and interested spectators. Among the many areas where stakeholder integration could affect the result of a project are planning, communication, risk management, and general project governance. Shafi et al. (2021) say that with an eye on how this integration advances effective project outcomes, it is important to investigate the theoretical foundations and empirical evidence from several industries to grasp the relevance of stakeholder integration in attaining these objectives. Usually, a project is deemed successful if its objectives are met within the allocated time and budget and simultaneously satisfy the expectations of all the participants (Zaman et al., 2023). However, including sustainability, stakeholder satisfaction, and long-term impacts makes defining a successful project more broad and complicated.

Stakeholder theory argued that the success of any project or company depends on the ability to manage the links and interests of many stakeholders, therefore offering the theoretical framework for stakeholder integration (Mariam et al., 2022). Most people think that Freeman (1984) officially developed stakeholder theory by arguing that businesses should seek to benefit their employees and maximize profits. Applied to projects, this concept contends that project managers should give stakeholder engagement and collaboration top priority if they are to reach both internal and external goals.

The integration of stakeholders helps control risk as well. Any project will inevitably include unknowns related to the scope, timetable, money, or outside factors like law changes or the market's health (Shahzad et al., 2023). Like customers or authorities, outside stakeholders may frequently highlight potential risks project teams overlook. Including stakeholders in the risk management process will help project managers to grasp the hazards better and develop strategies to minimize them. One wonderful idea would be to include community members' heads in the early warning systems of the construction project about social and environmental dangers that can drive up costs or create delays. Marrewijk et al. (2024) say stakeholder integration is just as crucial in resource allocation and decision-making. Stakeholder involvement and the probability that they will offer financial, human, or informational resources to a project show a positive association. In public sector projects or those involving many organizations, this is particularly crucial as different stakeholders—including government agencies, contractors, and community groups—may possess varied but vital resources for the project's success (Lin et al., 2024). Resource constraints or bottlenecks would be less likely if stakeholders participate in the decision-making process and resources are allocated correctly. Based on the above mentioned hypothesis, we have proposed the H1 of the study:

H1: There is a positive relationship between stakeholder integration and project success.

The conceptual model of the study is presented in Figure 1 mentioned below

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the study.

**Research Methodology:
Research Philosophy**

This study is based on the theory of positivism, which is a school of thought common in the natural sciences that says ideas should be supported by real-world proof (Mohajan, 2020). Positivism is based on the idea that there is an objective truth that can be studied separately from people's personal views. Strijker et al. (2020) says a realist approach works well for this study because it tries to separate the role of project governance as a bridge between the effects of internal factors (involving stakeholders, servant leadership, and environmental performance) on project success. Positivism says the only way to know something is to look at and measure something. The positivist model works well with this study since it uses planned polls and external sources to gather measurable data. This method uses statistical analysis to find links between causes and effects by focusing on how factors can be seen to interact with each other (Sürücü and Maslakci, 2020). This is especially useful in project management for determining what factors always lead to good projects in different situations.

Research Approach

The research method used in this study is called logical research. It is based on testing current ideas by developing hypotheses and doing empirical investigations. If one uses the logical method, one starts with a theory or set of assumptions and then uses facts to prove or debunk those assumptions (Straub et al., 2022). The study aims to discover how project governance affects the relationships between internal factors like involving stakeholders, environmental performance, servant leadership, and project success. That's why this method makes sense. The first step in the systematic, logical method is to do a full literature review. According to Ghauri et al. (2020) this is done to find well-known project management ideas and models. To test these theories, data from a broad group was used. These frames then shaped these theories. The study's assumptions were based on previous research that looked at the links between the factors of interest, such as environmental performance, project control, project success, and involving stakeholders.

Research Strategy

In this study, the researchers used a quantitative method, a great way to test ideas with hard numbers and look for links between factors (Cortina, 2020). Using a quantitative method, researchers collect and study measurable data to find links between project governance and internal factors like partner integration and project results. By using well-organized surveys to collect raw data, this method makes it possible to test theories accurately and repeatedly. Choosing a quantitative method is very important for a study to show links between causes and effects (Xiong, 2022).

Methods of Data collection

This study uses primary and secondary data collection methods to get a full picture of how

partner integration, and project governance affect project success. Using both types of data makes the findings more complete and in-depth, and the results can be checked against three different data sets.

Primary Data Collection: Primary data is taken from the field to get first-hand knowledge about the studied variables. This study uses an organized questionnaire poll to get first-hand information from people in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Pakistan, who are directly involved in large-scale development projects funded by the Annual Development Program (ADP). The questionnaire includes validated scales from prior research to measure the key constructs: **Project Success** (Pinto's 1986 scale with 14 items), and **Stakeholder Integration** (Plaza-Ubeda et al., 2009 scale with 16 items). The survey is completed by managers, supervisors, and subordinates working on ADP projects. Supervisors were asked to provide information on project governance, environmental performance, project success, and integrating stakeholders. Subordinates were asked to provide information on servant leadership. Each of these groups is given 300 surveys to ensure that the sample represents the target community well.

Secondary Data Collection: There were many places to find extra data to add to the original data. These included academic journals, government papers, and books. These sources help the study's research results by giving basic information about ADP programs and how they fit into history (Velte, 2023). For secondary statistics, government records were looked at to see what the ADP programs had accomplished and how they had changed over the past ten years.

Population

This study involves people who work on large-scale development projects in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Pakistan, that are backed by the Annual Development Program (ADP). The ADP is very important to Pakistan's economic growth because it provides a lot of money for social, educational, and infrastructure projects (Clark et al., 2021). Because these programs greatly impact national and area growth, it is very important to understand how they work.

Overall Population: The total population comprises ADP employees who have worked on different projects in the last ten years (2010–2021). The estimate was based on the idea that each project would have about 50 people working on it and that about 100 projects would start each year. The total number of people working on these projects was now around 5000. These projects have many different types and areas, such as buildings, education, healthcare, etc. Because of how big these projects are, they hired managers, engineers, directors, and support staff, among other jobs.

Target Population: The study focuses on a smaller group within this bigger group. After that, the list is cut down to megaprojects with costs over PKR 1 billion, which 35 KPK government departments manage. These projects are important because of their size, financial support, and possible impact on the area. One of the most interesting parts of the ADP is the university growth projects, which have been given more than PKR 1 billion in funds. This is met by twenty university projects, almost half of the whole. Each project hires about fifty people for about a thousand people. The study is about people who work for the Hazara and Mardan Divisions of KPK. The ADP backs many large-scale research projects in universities of these areas. This study focuses on managers, and workers who work on these projects because they are important as project stakeholders significant for project success.

Sampling: 300 questionnaires were divided among Managers, Supervisors, and subordinates working on university projects in Hazara and Mardan Division only. This approach ensures that everyone in the study's target group has an equal chance to take part (Leavy, 2022). Management, managers, and workers were used to divide the sample into three groups. This way, the study can include points of view from different project management and government levels.

Data Analysis:
4.1 Item loadings

Table 1 shows the item loadings for each of the constructs under investigation. Two items, SI5, and SI10, were dropped due to loadings of less than 0.6, while the rest of the items had loadings of 0.6 and above, as set by Jordan and Spiess (2019) and Minghua (2022).

Table 1: Item loadings

Items	PS	SI
PS1	0.706	
PS2	0.638	
PS3	0.672	
PS4	0.688	
PS5	0.778	
PS6	0.686	
PS7	0.775	
PS8	0.775	
PS9	0.755	
PS10	0.725	
PS11	0.717	
PS12	0.761	
PS13	0.661	
PS14	0.658	
SI1		0.672
SI2		0.749
SI3		0.709
SI4		0.674
SI6		0.713
SI7		0.703
SI8		0.642
S9		0.711
S11		0.838
SI12		0.776
SI13		0.791
SI14		0.727
SI15		0.711
SI16		0.742

Note. SI= stakeholder integration= PS= project success; PG= project governance.

4.2 Construct Reliability

In SmartPLS, three critical reliability estimates are Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), and rho_A. Cronbach's Alpha measures the internal consistency of items, with a threshold of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019) indicating acceptable reliability, but it assumes that all items contribute equally to the construct. Composite Reliability (CR), preferred in structural equation

modeling, accounts for the differing contributions of each item, with values above 0.7 signifying good reliability (Graciola et al., 2020). rho_A is considered a more accurate reliability measure between Cronbach's Alpha and CR, as it better represents the construct's reliability even if the items vary in contribution. The acceptable values for rho_A are greater than 0.7 (Graciola et al., 2020). These estimates ensure robust measurement models in SmartPLS. It can be observed that (Table 2) all the values for Cronbach alpha, CR, and rho_A are within acceptable ranges, suggesting acceptable reliability of the scales used.

Table 2: Construct reliability

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)
Project success	0.926	0.927	0.936
Stakeholder integration	0.931	0.933	0.940

4.3 Convergent Validity

A key indicator of convergent validity in structural equation modeling (SEM), including SmartPLS, is average variance extracted (AVE). It shows the degree of latent concept explanation for the variance of its indicators. An AVE score of 0.5 or above indicates that, on average, the construct captures more than half of the variance from its indicators, therefore indicating that the items are well-correlated and essentially reflect the construct. If AVE is less than 0.5, it could mean that the measurement model has to be refined since the indicators do not converge effectively to evaluate the desired notion (Hair et al., 2019). Since all AVEs in the present study were above 0.5, we are confident that the scale had reasonable convergent validity. See Table 3 for details.

Table 3: Convergent validity

Variable	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Project success	0.512
Stakeholder integration	0.529

4.4 Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

In contrast to HTMT, a traditional approach is that of the Fornell-Larcker criterion, which evaluates discriminant validity using a comparison between the square root of the AVE of every construct and its correlations with other constructs. Establishing discriminant validity requires the square root of a concept's AVE to be greater than its correlation with every construct in the model (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). This approach guarantees that, with its indicators, a construct shares more variance than with other constructions. But, particularly in more complicated models for identifying discriminant validity problems, it is considered less sensitive than the HTMT method.

4.5 Collinearity Diagnostics

Variance inflation factor (VIF) is a metric that identifies multicollinearity between independent variables. It shows the extent of the inflation in variance of a regression coefficient brought about by the correlation with other factors. A VIF score of more than 5 usually indicates

strong multicollinearity, in which case the variable is entirely linked with others and could produce instability in the regression estimations (Becker et al., 2015). Table 6 shows that all VIF scores were less than 5.

Table 6: Collinearity diagnostics

Item	VIF
PS1	2.071
PS2	1.751
PS3	1.808
PS4	2.003
PS5	2.456
PS6	1.876
PS7	2.770
PS8	2.450
PS9	2.883
PS10	2.432
PS11	2.319
PS12	2.699
PS13	1.827
PS14	1.942
SI1	2.082
SI2	2.405
SI3	2.258
SI4	1.862
SI6	2.321
SI7	2.728
SI8	2.003
SI9	2.442
SI11	3.704
SI12	2.901
SI13	2.932
SI14	2.349
SI15	2.052
SI16	2.391

4.6 Path Diagram of CFA Output

Figure 1 portrays the outcome of the PLS-SEM algorithm, highlighting the effects of stakeholder integration on project success through project governance. It also shows the moderating roles of servant leadership and environmental performance.

Figure 1: CFA Output Diagram

4.7 R-Square

Table 7 shows the R-square statistics for the proposed model. It shows that the model explains 71.2 percent of the variance in Stakeholder Integration and 58.2 percent of the variance in project success.

Table 7: R-Square statistics

Dependent variable	R-square	R-square adjusted
Stakeholder Integration	0.712	0.708
Project success	0.582	0.577

4.8 F-Square

The f^2 (Effect Size) gauges how an independent variable affects a dependent variable. It is usually understood as small, medium, and high effect sizes. Accordingly, values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 are often modest (Hair et al., 2019). A more significant influence on the outcome variable suggests a greater f^2 for the predictor. See Table 8 for results.

Table 8: F-Square statistics

Variable	PS	SI
Project success	1	
Stakeholder integration	0.470	1

Note. SI= stakeholder integration; PS= project success;

4.9 Direct Effects

It can be observed from Table 9 that all direct effects were significant. First, the direct impact of Stakeholder integration on Project success was significant ($p < 0.001$), supporting H1. Similarly, Stakeholder integration showed a significant positive influence on Project governance ($p < 0.001$), supporting H2. H3 was also supported as Project governance had a positive influence on Project success ($p < 0.001$).

Table 9: Direct effects based on SEM

Relationship	β	SD	T statistics	P values
Stakeholder integration -> Project success	0.381	0.107	3.557	0.000

5. Findings and Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to examine how stakeholder integration impact project success, with a focus on ADP sponsored projects. In particular, the study set out to provide light on the intricate interplay between these factors as they pertain to massive development initiatives in Pakistan, a setting marked by distinct institutional and economic obstacles. The key findings of this study highlight several important connections. Firstly, integrating stakeholders significantly improved project success rates, supporting the idea that including stakeholders in decision-making processes improves results in general. Also, by providing frameworks and accountability mechanisms, project governance mediates the impact of stakeholder integration on project success is further strengthened (Young et al., 2020).

The theoretical and practical implications of each discovery is going to be analyzed in relation to prior research in this particular chapter. Stakeholder engagement is key to effective projects as mentioned in the literature (Bahadorestani et al., 2020). But this study contributes to that body of knowledge by examining such dynamics in developing countries like Pakistan. Project management techniques can be adjusted for better performance in complex and resource constrained settings if results are interpreted in light of existing theories.

Theoretical and Managerial Contributions

Results showed a positive relationship between stakeholder integration and project success, hinting that involving stakeholders in project decision-making and processes increases project success odds. Consistent with previous research, this result highlights the importance of involving stakeholders in project management; for example, Urbinati et al. (2021) assert that better project execution is achieved by involving stakeholders' perspectives early on because it helps with conflict reduction and consensus building. Engagement of stakeholders in a project increases communication and collaboration which improves risk management and resource allocation which improves project performance. These findings support the thesis that stakeholder engagement is a strategic (rather than a necessary evil) component of successful projects. All interested parties should have their interests considered and managed for a project or organization to be a success, according to Freeman's (1984) stakeholder theory which the findings support. Theoretically, this also pertains to project management: seeking out, understanding and satisfying the needs and expectations of different stakeholders may help managers improve project outcomes (Urton and Murray, 2021). Stakeholder integration is an important ingredient of a successful project and results from this study support this viewpoint. Decreased probability of delays and disagreements common derailers is achieved, in particular, through engagement of stakeholders in project teams to anticipate issues and reconcile project objectives with stakeholder expectations.

Although prior research indicates that stakeholder integration has a positive effect, this study reveals the advantage is bigger in the context of Pakistan's large-scale development initiatives. Limited resources, political intervention and cultural variety are other common barriers that developing nations face. These factors may complicate stakeholder participation. For instance, Eriksen et al. (2021) note that conflicting cultural norms and bureaucratic red tape may prevent stakeholders from being involved in decision-making and communication in developing nations. Active stakeholder integration can improve project success especially in challenging environments such as Pakistan, as the present study suggests (Rasool et al., 2022). This supports the idea that stakeholder engagement is a universally beneficial practice, though the methods and intensity of engagement may need to be tailored to suit specific cultural and institutional contexts.

The study also found that project governance significantly mediates the relationship between stakeholder integration and project success. This means that while providing a formal

framework for decision making, accountability and risk management, project governance processes and structures facilitate stakeholder engagement in positive project outcomes. This result is consistent with past studies which highlighted the importance of governance in guaranteeing a project success. Projects are more likely to achieve their goals if they are well-governed, which optimizes resources and defines roles and duties (Dorasamy, 2025). Governance frameworks help organize and structure stakeholder input to enable systematic management of expectations and implementation of stakeholder feedback. Theoretical frameworks for project governance shed light on its mediating role and propose that projects are better managed, coordinated and overseen when proper governance structures are in place. Handling risks and conflicts and aligning project objectives with organizational strategy are two main functions of governance frameworks in project management. Through its mediating role, project governance ensures that stakeholder concerns are looked at in a manner that improves general effectiveness and also lessens the likelihood of failure and closes the gap between stakeholder inputs and project outputs (Ika and Pinto, 2022). In line with these theoretical frameworks, findings support the view that effective project governance is required to transform stakeholder involvement into a successful outcome.

Compared with prior research, this study advances existing knowledge by demonstrating that project governance in developing nations can facilitate stakeholder integration in concrete ways. Mökander et al. (2021) note that governance frameworks can provide for accountability and decision making in contexts where institutional institutions are not sufficient. The results confirm this claim, noting that good project governance remains crucial to limit the impact of stakeholder integration on project success, particularly in a country such as Pakistan where political will for governance is low. These findings suggest that good governance is an essential component for better project results in less regulated contexts than in more regulated ones.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical issues must be thought through before a study project is finished. This is especially important when getting first-hand information from real people (Ahmad and Raja, 2021). It was important to follow ethical standards when gathering information from managers, bosses, and workers working on ADP projects in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Pakistan, to protect their rights, privacy, and honesty. The subjects were fully told about the study's purpose, methods, and goals before collecting data. People were also told that they had no obligation to take part and could quit at any time without any consequences. Strijker et al. (2020) says giving people a written permission form is a good way to ensure they know what they agree to. The study only included people who read the clearance form and voluntarily agreed to participate.

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